

Postgraduate training of healthcare professionals at Medical University – Sofia: financing and challenges

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Abstract

After completing a six-year undergraduate medical program, during which young doctors acquire both theoretical knowledge and practical skills, they build the necessary foundation for independently addressing organizational, preventive, diagnostic, and other professional tasks. They then undergo postgraduate training to acquire a medical specialty in the Bulgarian healthcare system. This training involves mastering advanced theoretical knowledge and practical skills in a specific area of medical science and practice and concludes with a state examination. This article presents and analyzes the dynamics of financing postgraduate training of healthcare professionals in Bulgaria.

Keywords

funding, postgraduate training, trends, young doctors

Introduction

An individual's need for self-affirmation is closely connected to their professional development and success. Therefore, career choice is a complex decision-making process shaped by both social and personal factors. It reflects not only societal needs but also the individual's interests and capabilities (Vodenitcharov 1986; Kirkov et al. 2024).

This is especially true for the postgraduate training of young medical professionals. After completing their six-year undergraduate medical education, during which they gain theoretical knowledge and practical skills and thus prepare to independently solve organizational, prophylactic, medical-diagnostic, and other professional tasks (Kirkov 2023), young doctors take

state exams, according to the curriculum and the Unified State Requirements, and acquire the right to practice the medical profession (Law on Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria 2020). Doctors who wish to specialize must complete postgraduate training, which lasts between one and five years depending on the specialty. This pathway enables professional differentiation among doctors and helps address both current and future healthcare needs in Bulgaria (Vodenitcharov 1992; Kirkov et al. 2024).

Postgraduate training for acquiring a specialty in Bulgaria's healthcare system involves developing advanced theoretical knowledge and practical skills in a defined area of medical science and practice. This training concludes with a state examination. The duration

of training is defined in the official nomenclature of specialties and follows a framework curriculum for each specialty, as approved by the Minister of Health. Theoretical education is provided by accredited medical universities under the Higher Education Act. Practical training is delivered in approved “training bases”—medical institutions accredited for postgraduate clinical training of doctors, dentists, pharmacists, and healthcare professionals (Law on Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria 2020; Regulation No. 1 2015).

Medical specialties in Bulgaria are classified into three categories: clinical, non-clinical, and dental. These are acquired upon successful completion of the required curriculum and after passing both theoretical and practical exams before a state examination commission appointed by the Minister of Health. Clinical specialties involve direct diagnostic or therapeutic activities with patients. According to Supplementary Regulation No. 1 of 2015 by the Ministry of Health, there are 78 clinical specialties. Non-clinical specialties, in which trainees do not perform direct patient care or diagnostic procedures, are 56. An additional 13 specialties are designated for individuals qualified as dentists.

The number of state-funded specialization positions is determined twice a year by the Ministry of Health, based on national health strategy priorities and workforce needs in specific specialties. For clinical specialties, the state covers both theoretical and practical training costs, with a maximum monthly training fee of 230 BGN. Additionally, trainees receive financial support equivalent to 2.5 times the national minimum wage, along with the employer’s social security contributions for the duration of their training. In the specialty of general medicine, the Ministry of Health provides training institutions with enhanced financial support—1.2 times the base amount of 2.5 minimum wages—plus corresponding social security contributions. For non-clinical specialties, training costs are similarly covered, with fees capped at 230 BGN per month. An exception exists for the specialization of dentists: for these professionals, the maximum fee for practical training is increased to 460 BGN (Regulation No. 1 2015; Ministry of Health—Republic of Bulgaria; National Health Strategy 2021–2030 2021).

The purpose of this article is to present and analyze the financing of postgraduate education in the healthcare system of the Republic of Bulgaria for the period 2018–2022.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set and implemented:

- Study and analysis of the dynamics of financial information for specialization places in clinical specialties, financed by the state.
- Study and analysis of the dynamics of financial information for specialization places in non-clinical specialties, financed by the state.
- Study and analysis of the dynamics of financial information for specialization places for dentists, financed by the state.

Materials and methodology of the research

The object of this scientific study is the dynamics of financial resources for postgraduate training of health professionals, based on data from the Medical University – Sofia for the period 2018–2022, as well as the factors influencing it.

A combination of sociological, statistical, and documentary research methods was employed.

Quantitative data were analyzed using the SPSS 17.0 statistical software package. Microsoft Office tools were used for tabulation, data visualization, and graphical presentation of results.

Results and discussion

A large amount of information is required to carry out any analytical process. Financial data, typically derived from accounting systems, are particularly valuable because they are based on specific, quantifiable facts. These data are expressed in monetary terms, enabling aggregation, comparison, and various forms of analysis. The creation of an adequately functioning information system is a priority for every management (Holloway 2006).

Table 1 presents the trends in financial resources allocated by the Ministry of Health to Medical University – Sofia for clinical specialty training during the period 2018–2022. Notably, the funds provided by the state for clinical specialties increased nearly fivefold over this period. The trend of increase is consistent, with annual growth of over 30% compared to the previous year. The financial analysis shows that the increase in 2022 was the most substantial. Compared to 2021, the state’s funding rose by 50%, despite a small change in the number of trainees completing their programs during this period. The main reason for this is the increase in funds allocated per trainee in state-funded training positions.

The most significant increase occurred in 2022, with funding doubling compared to 2021. This sharp growth was not due to a substantial change in the number of trainees but rather a deliberate increase in state funding per clinical specialty trainee. The financial growth trend continued steadily, culminating in a dramatic 95.88% rise from 2021 to 2022. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ministry of Health placed greater emphasis on supporting healthcare professionals. The essential role of medical personnel during the health crisis was widely recognized, leading to policy changes aimed at reinforcing postgraduate training programs. As a result, state-financed training allocations increased significantly after 2021, reaching a total of 323,589.55 BGN by the end of 2022.

Table 2 presents the financial dynamics of state funding allocated by the Ministry of Health to Medical University – Sofia for non-clinical specialties and specialties for individuals with the professional qualification „Doctor of Dental Medicine“ over the period 2018–2022. Unlike clinical specialties, these categories do not exhibit a consistent

Table 1. Funds for clinical specialties allocated for the period 2018–2022.

Year	Number of postgraduates who completed training	Financial resources allocated for training in clinical specialties in BGN	Growth rate in %
2018	420	58,114.63	–
2019	319	96,707.23	66.40%
2020	283	12,917.52	31.23%
2021	258	165,185.04	30.15%
2022	295	323,589.55	95.88%
Total	1575	770,513.97	–

Table 2. Funds for non-clinical specialties allocated for the period 2018–2022.

Year	Number of postgraduates who completed training	Financial resources allocated for training in non-clinical specialties and specialties for persons with the professional qualification „Doctor of Dental Medicine“ in BGN	Growth rate in %
2018	50	33,881.14	–
2019	73	26,427.07	- 22.00%
2020	55	47,140.42	78.45%
2021	46	91,585.03	94.28%
2022	70	73,319.69	- 19.94%
Total	294	272,353.35	–

growth trend. Instead, the financial data show significant year-to-year fluctuations, including negative growth in two of the analyzed years—2019 and 2022—during which funding decreased notably, likely in favor of clinical specialties. Financial analysis reveals that approximately 80% of the allocated funds within this category are directed toward dental specialties, while the remaining 20% support other non-clinical specialties. It is good practice for the state to allocate significant financial resources for the postgraduate training of dental specialists, but it should not be at the expense of other non-clinical specialists. Continuing postgraduate training in dentistry seeks to implement the principle of integrating dental and oral health into general health by overcoming the differences between dental and human medicine. It is essential that dental specialists have the necessary knowledge and competencies to ensure the health needs of the population through the medical care they provide, including influencing the social factors of health in order to contribute to improving the quality of life of the population they serve.

Table 3 summarizes the dynamics of state-funded financial resources allocated for postgraduate training in clinical, non-clinical, and dental specialties, clearly showing an increasing trend in funding from 2018 to 2022. Over this period, the total amount of budget funds increased approximately 4.5 times, exceeding 1 million BGN, despite a one-third decrease in the absolute number of specialists trained. This demonstrates the state's commitment to investing in postgraduate training and improving the pay of young professionals

within Bulgaria's healthcare system. When analyzing the relative shares of funding throughout 2018–2022, there is a noticeable increase in financial support for clinical specialties each year. Conversely, funding for non-clinical specialties declined in 2019 and again in 2022, which corresponds to a lower number of postgraduates admitted to state-funded positions during those specific years. These patterns highlight both a strategic focus on clinical specialties and the need for balanced investment across all specialty areas.

Inference

The training of medical specialists is linked to the health needs of the population and the need to ensure an optimal ratio between the individual categories of medical personnel. In this regard, targeted efforts are needed to increase the number of opportunities for postgraduate training and acquisition of professional qualifications so that the education system can begin to meet the identified needs of the health system for certain types of medical specialists in the medium and long term. The quality of human resources in health systems is determined to the maximum extent by their professional training and preparation, which is a complex and multifaceted process of national importance for each country. Investment in postgraduate training within the healthcare system is essential to ensure the acquisition of specialized professional knowledge, skills, and competencies required for medical practice and specialty development.

Table 3. Summary data for the period 2018–2022.

Year	Financial resources allocated for training in clinical specialties in BGN	Relative share in %	Financial resources allocated for training in non-clinical specialties and specialties for persons with the professional qualification „Doctor of Dental Medicine“ in BGN	Relative share %	Total in BGN
2018	58,114.63	7.54%	33,881.14	12.44%	91,995.77
2019	96,707.23	12.55%	26,427.07	9.70%	123,134.30
2020	126,917.52	16.47%	47,140.42	17.31%	174,057.94
2021	165,185.04	21.44%	91,585.03	33.63%	256,770.07
2022	323,589.60	42.00%	73,319.69	26.92%	396,909.24
Total	770,513.97	100%	272,353.35	100%	1,042,867.32

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of empirical data regarding the financing trends for postgraduate training of health professionals in the Republic of Bulgaria, it is evident that the state should prioritize targeted budget financing for specialties exhibiting negative trends. Particular attention is needed to improve the specialization process in general medicine, given the current shortage of primary healthcare physicians in

this field. Additionally, updating the training programs for both undergraduate and postgraduate students in human medicine is crucial to meet evolving healthcare demands.

Therefore, the provision and production of quality medical personnel is of strategic importance for every society in order to carry out health activities based on the best examples of medical knowledge and health practice, in accordance with ethical principles and norms and based on scientific evidence.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.